

**CLINICO-MYCOLOGICAL CORRELATION OF DERMATOPHYTIC
INFECTIONS IN PATIENT ATTENDING TO A TERTIARY CARE
HOSPITAL**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The number of patients with diabetes and other chronic diseases, immunocompromised patients, HIV-positive people, and age-related alterations in immune response have all contributed to the growth of dermatophytosis infections in recent decades. Therefore, the study was carried out to identify the dermatophytic infection in clinically suspected patients attending to a tertiary care hospital.

Materials and methods: 50 clinically suspected cases were included in the study according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Skin scrapings, crusts and clipped nail or plucked hair samples were collected from the patients. Specimens were examined microscopically by KOH mount then cultured on SDA and DTM. Upon growth, LPCB mount, slide culture and urease tests were performed.

Results: 1.78:1 male female ratio was reported. Most common affected group was 31-45 years. Tinea corporis was most common type observed in male and female followed by Tinea cruris and Tinea capitis. A total of 28 cases tested positive using both microscopy and culture methods. 7 cases were found positive through microscopy but were negative in the culture tests. 2 cases showed negative results in microscopy but returned positive results in culture. 13 (26%) cases were negative by both microscopy as well as culture. Among 35 isolates, *T.mentagrophytes* were the commonest followed by *T.rubrum* and *T. tonsurans*.

Conclusion: The present study highlighted maximum isolates were *T.mentagrophytes* followed by *T.rubrum* and *T.tonsurans* from clinically suspected dermatophytosis patients.

Key Words: Dermatophytes, SSKOH mount, LPCB mount

INTRODUCTION: In order to survive, dermatophytes break down and absorb nutrients from keratin, which evolved to rely on human or animal infection^[1]. A dermatophyte can be classified as either ecophilic, zoophilic, or geophilic based on its ecological characteristics^[2]. In dermatophytes, the snake-like appearance is called tinea (worm)^[3]. Among women, infection is more common due to progesterone inhibiting fungi's development^[4]. Hair, nails, and skin are frequently infected with Dermatophytes. Symptoms of infection include itching, erythema, induration, and scaling. As a result of dermatophyte infection, the host may experience a variety of reactions depending on its response to fungal metabolic products, as well as the virulence of the organisms causing the infection and the environment it is exposed to. Besides *Epidermophyton floccosum*, there are other species in *Microsporum* (such as *M. gypseum*, *M. canis*, *M. nanum*) and *Trycophyton* (such as *T. rubrum*, *T. mentagrophytes*, *T. verrucosum*)^[5,6]. Therefore the study was carried out to correlate between clinical presentation and the isolates ad to start early treatment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS :

Type of study: Prospective study

Place of study: Department of Dermatology and Venereology, Department of Microbiology, MGM Medical College and Hospital Navi Mumbai

Period of study: From December 2020- December 2021

Ethical approved: The study was approved by Institutional Ethics Committee (N-IEC/2019/SC/7/99).

Total number of samples included: A total number of 50 clinically suspected cases obtained from the patients attending dermatology and venereology department were included in the study according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Patients on antifungal drugs were excluded from the study.

Collection of Samples: After cleaning the affected area with 70% ethyl alcohol, skin scraping, crusts and clipped nail or plucked hair were collected in clean white paper packets. Skin samples were obtained by scraping the seemingly healthy tissue around the inflamed lesion margin. By taking clippings of the contaminated portion and scraping under the nail, nail specimens were collected.

Processing of samples: Direct microscopic examination was done by KOH mount at various concentration (10%, 20%, 40%). Following direct microscopic examination, the samples were inoculated on SDA slant and incubated for 25 for up to four weeks. The samples were also inoculated on dermatophyte test medium. When no growth was detected after four weeks, the case was classified as negative for fungal growth. Macroscopic examination of the culture was done by colony characteristics (both obverse and reverse).

Fig no 1 : Growth of *T. mentagrophytes* on SDA

Fig no 2 : LPCB mount of *T. mentagrophytes*.

Microscopic examination of the culture was done by tease mount/needle mount and LPCB mount prepared for further identification (**Fig 1 & Fig 2**). Slide culture was performed. Urease test was performed to distinguish between *Trichophyton mentagrophyte* and *Trichophyton rubrum*.

RESULTS:

Demographic distribution:

Age wise distribution: The total number of cases were distributed between the range 12-59 years. Mean age was 31.36. The most common group affected was 31-45 years with 26 cases (52%) followed by 16-30 years with 14 cases (28%) and ≤ 15 years with 6 cases (12%). Least common age group affected was 46-60 with 4 cases (8%).

Sex wise distribution: Out of 50 clinically suspected cases, the males were most commonly affected with 32 cases (64%) than females with 18 cases (36%). The male to female ratio was 1.78:1.

Clinical correlation

Fig no 3: Gender wise distribution with clinical correlation

Tinea corporis was more common in males with 18 cases (72%) than in females with 7 cases (28%). Tinea cruris was more in common in male with 9 cases (60%) than in females with 6 cases (40%). Tinea capitis was more common in males with 5 cases (100%). *Tinea unguium* was more common in males with 4 cases (80%) than in females with 1 case (20%). (**Figure no 3**)

Fig no 4: KOH mount and Culture results

Fig no 5 : Growth of *T. mentagrophytes* on SDA

Microscopic and culture examination: Out of 50 clinically suspected cases of dermatophytosis, fungi were demonstrated in 37 cases (74%) either by direct microscopy and/or culture. 28 cases (56%) were positive by both microscopy and culture. 7 (14%) cases were positive by microscopy and negative by culture. 2 cases (4%) were negative by microscopy but culture positive. 13 cases (26%) were negative by both microscopy as well as culture. (**Figure no 4**). Growth was observed Dermatophyte test medium. (**fig no 5**)

Fig no 6 : Christensen's medium showing colour change to deep red indicates positive result whereas no colour change indicates negative result

Fig no 7: Percentage of species isolated

Urease test was positive by all the isolates (22 isolates) of *T.mentagrophyte* and negative by *T.rubrum*. (Depicted in fig no 6)

Out of total 35 isolates, *T. mentagrophyte* was the commonest with 22 isolates (62.85%) followed by *T. rubrum* 11(31.42%) and *T. tonsurans* 2 (5.71%). (Depicted in Figure no 7)

Discussion: In the present study, 50 clinically suspected cases of dermatophytosis attending to Dermatology and Venereology outpatient department of MGM Hospital, MGM Medical College, Kamothe, Navi Mumbai included in the study.

Age distribution: The present study showed that dermatophytosis was more common in the age group of 30-45 years (52%) followed by 16-30 years (28%), which is comparable with the other studies done by Bokhari MA, Veer P, Soniya Mahajan, whereas Rekha Sharma has reported that the most common age group affected was 16-30 years followed by 31-45 years. The highest incidence in adults aged 31-45 may be due to increased physical activity and increased opportunity for exposure

Sex-wise distribution: In the present study, males (64 %) were more commonly affected than females (36 percent). Male to female ratio was 1.78:1 which is comparable with other studies done by Huda MM, Bindu V, Grover S, Rekha Sharma *et al.* whereas Nanda H reported females were more commonly affected than males with male to female ratio being 0.13:1. Male predominance may be due to increased outdoor physical activities and increased opportunity for exposure to infection than female.

Clinical findings

Tinea corporis: In the present study, *tinea corporis* was the commonest clinical type encountered (50 %) followed by *tinea cruris* (30 %), *tinea capitis* (10 %) and *tinea unguium*. Males were predominantly affected (72 %) than females (28 percent), which is comparable with the studies done by Venkatesan G (64.8 %).

Tinea cruris: In the present study, *tinea cruris* was the second most common clinical type (30 %). Males (60 %) were commonly affected than females (40 %) which is comparable with the study done by Siddappa K, Mishra M. and Sen SS.

Tinea capitis: In the present study *Tinea capitis* was more common in males (100 percent) which is comparable with other studies done by Kumar AG (78 %) and Kalla G (85.5%).

Tinea unguium: In the present study onychomycosis was more common in males (80 percent) than females (20 percent) which is comparable with the other studies done by Grover S., whereas Cordeiro RA and Nanda H in their studies reported that females were commonly affected than males.

In the present study, out of 50 clinically suspected cases of dermatophytosis, 40 cases (80 percent) were positive for fungi either by KOH and/or culture. 28 (56%) was positive by both KOH and culture. 7 cases (14%) were positive by KOH and negative by culture, 2 cases (4%) negative by KOH but positive by culture. 13 cases (26%) were negative by both KOH as well as culture which is comparable with other studies done by Nanda H and Karmakar S. This variation could be due to non- viability of fungal elements in some of the cases.

In present study, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* 22 (62.86 %) was the commonest aetiological agent in majority of clinical type followed by *Trichophyton rubrum* 11 (31.42 percent) and *Trichophyton tonsurans* 2 (5.71 percent) which is comparable with the study done by Bhabani S. T. P.

Conclusion: Several factors contribute to the high prevalence of dermatophytosis in India, including the warm and humid climate that favors fungal growth, and socioeconomic factors, including overcrowding and lack of access to healthcare. *There are numerous keratinized tissues that can be affected by Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, including skin, hair, and nails. Due to the large number of enzymes produced by *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, it is capable of invading

and digesting these tissues with ease. Health care providers' awareness and improved diagnostic facilities have led to better detection of *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* infections.

Limitations: Single centric study, sample size was less.

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